

Integration of Science, Education, and Industry: High steps for Future Innovation.

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Annotation: The article addresses a critical shift in the relationship between education, science, and production as society transitions from an industrial to a post-industrial framework. The theoretical comprehension of integration suggests a focus on how these domains interconnect and influence each other.

Key words: integration, education, science, production, society, collaboration, competitive, global labor market, gradual tendency, interaction, sociofunctional approaches.

Introduction. In the rapidly evolving landscape of the 21st century, the integration of science, education, and industry has become a crucial imperative for fostering innovation, economic development, and social progress. The synergy between these three sectors creates a dynamic ecosystem that not only enhances the learning experience but also prepares students for real-world challenges. This article explores the importance of this integration, its benefits, and strategic approaches to achieving a harmonious relationship among science, education, and industry.

The problem of integrating education, science and production in modern literature is developed quite narrowly, the relationship between science and production, on the one hand, and education, on the other, is traditionally considered. This relationship is characterized as follows: education reflects only the changes occurring in science and production. At the same time, at every historical stage in the development of society, the connections and relations between science, education and production are manifested differently, which requires a more detailed analysis of the existing integration. Material and methods. Integration (from Lat. Integration - restoration, replenishment, from inter – whole)

- the concept of systems theory, interpreted both ontologically state of connectedness, integrity of the individual parts and functions of the system. If we consider education and science as a single system, it becomes obvious that its development, like the development of any other system, is characterized by integration trends at various levels. This allows you to combine the philosophical-anthropological and sociofunctional approaches to the essence of education and science. Integration in the system "education - science - production" should be understood as the process of interpenetration, mutual enrichment of education and science as a system in order to best meet the needs of employers and society as a whole. Results and discussion. The prerequisites for the development of integration in education, science and industry are changes in the political, regulatory, economic, social and cultural spheres at different stages of development of society.

The integration of education and production begins to take shape even in the industrial period of the development of society, when there is an increase in the role of education to the level of the most important production prerequisite, which does not contradict the socio-philosophical concept of development, according to which the mode of production is reduced only to the production of material goods. In this case, science acts as a form of social consciousness and the sphere of activity of people. Gradually, science becomes a full-fledged participant in the relationship between education and production as a form of direct productive power. During the period of industrial development of the society, quite a strong development of integration in the system of "education - science - production" is noted, namely, the development of a system for planning the graduation of specialists and training of scientific personnel in accordance with the requirements of production, a developed system of departmental universities, a network of educational, scientific and industrial complexes and etc. At the transition stage (from the industrial development of society to post-industrial development or a knowledge-based society), the main achievements in the existing integration between education, science and production were lost. The main reason is the fact that changes in the development of society occurred in conjunction with a change

in the planned, administrative-command and market economies, which could not but have an impact on all areas of activity, including education and science. Despite the negative trends in the system “education - science – production” in the process of transition to the post-industrial development of society, one cannot but note the positive aspects in the development of integration at the present stage: - a gradual tendency to change the mechanism of interaction “supplier - consumer” to “partnership relations” to achieve mutual goals between education, science and industry; - development of modern directions and forms of integration in the system “education - science - production”, such as public-private partnerships, corporate education, scientific and industrial structures (business incubators, technoparks, technopolises, etc.).

Long-term growth of industrial companies largely depends on their integration with higher education and science to satisfy the advanced demands of the global economy. Therefore, collaboration between higher education and industry is at the forefront of academic programs, including those focusing on financial managers. The ‘higher education – science – industry’ triangle, however, often lacks joint efforts to develop degree programs aimed at solving real life problems. The paper aims at analyzing the integrative model of collaboration in this triangle and eliminating the existing gaps by developing guidelines for an effective training of professional financial managers under the university degree programs.

The Importance of Integration

Real-World Applications: One of the key benefits of integrating science and education with industry is the emphasis on practical, real-world applications of theoretical knowledge. By exposing students to industry practices and challenges, educational institutions can provide a comprehensive learning experience that prepares graduates for the workforce.

Innovation and Research: Collaboration between educational institutions and industries fosters a culture of innovation. Research conducted in partnership with

industry not only drives technological advancement but also allows for the sharing of resources, knowledge, and expertise. This collaboration results in the development of cutting-edge solutions to contemporary problems.

Skill Development: The integration of these sectors enables the development of critical skills that are essential for success in the modern workforce. Students acquire not only technical expertise but also soft skills such as teamwork, communication, and problem-solving. When educational programs incorporate industry standards and practices, graduates are better equipped to meet the demands of employers.

Economic Growth: A strong alliance between science, education, and industry contributes significantly to economic growth. By fostering a skilled workforce and driving innovation, this integration helps create jobs, enhance productivity, and stimulate overall economic development. Regions that prioritize these partnerships often see an increase in both local and global competitiveness.

Strategies for Effective Integration

Curriculum Development: Educational institutions should collaborate with industry stakeholders to develop curricula that reflect current industry needs and emerging trends. By incorporating hands-on experiences, internships, and co-op programs, students can gain valuable insights and skills that make them more marketable to employers.

Research Partnerships: Establishing research partnerships between universities and industries can facilitate knowledge transfer and support the commercialization of research findings. Joint research projects, grants, and funding opportunities can enhance the capacity for innovation and address industry-specific challenges.

Workforce Development Programs: Developing workforce training programs that align with industry requirements is vital. Vocational training and community colleges can play a significant role in preparing individuals for technical positions, offering specialized training that meets local industry needs.

Networking Events and Conference: Organizing networking events, workshops, and conferences can foster relationships between educators, researchers, and industry professionals. These interactions can lead to collaborations, mentorship opportunities, and knowledge exchange.

Technology Integration: Leveraging technology in education can enhance learning experiences and facilitate collaboration. Online platforms, simulations, and virtual labs can provide students with access to resources and tools that mirror industry practices. In the industrial era, education often emphasized producing a workforce equipped with specific skills for manufacturing and production. However, as society evolves into a post-industrial phase, characterized by advancements in technology, information, and services, the integration of education and science with production must adapt.

This transition likely calls for a more holistic approach, where interdisciplinary knowledge and innovative skill sets are crucial. The article may delve into aspects such as curriculum Changes, how educational programs have evolved to include more science and technology courses that prepare students for a rapidly changing job market. Collaboration between Sector: The need for stronger ties between educational institutions, research organizations, and industries to foster innovation and practical applications of scientific research. Lifelong Learning: The emphasis on continuous education and re-skilling in response to the fast pace of technological advancements and changing job requirements. New Educational Models including exploration of alternative educational approaches, such as experiential learning, internships, and project-based learning, which align more closely with real-world applications.

Societal Impact: Consideration of how these changes affect social structures, economic development, and individual career trajectories in a post-industrial context. Universities are endowed with independence in integrating education and science in the world. For example, in terms of increasing scientific indicators in production, academic and scientific independence, independent determination of

their scientific direction and forms of conduct research, educational institutions have the approach to work and management of education and research too. In this regard, we are also declining the functions of state control in the field of education and science year by year as well as creating ample opportunities for freedom of scientific activity. As a result of the on-going works to ensure the integration of education and science, overcoming the existing restrictions on the involvement of talented young people in scientific activities, the organization of research on the basis of PhD and strengthening scientific capacity and selection of highly qualified persons are being created to further enhance the prestige of scientific institutions and form new scientific institutions in the country. As a result of science management is supported a number of initiatives to establish cooperation between universities and research institutes. One of the most important events in the country is also the establishment of both financial incentives and advocacy to raise the social status of scientific and scientific-pedagogical persons.

Conclusion

The integration of science, education, and industry is essential for creating a sustainable future that promotes innovation and economic growth. By fostering collaboration among these sectors, we can build a robust ecosystem that nurtures talent, drives research, and addresses the complex challenges of our time. As we move forward, it is imperative for policymakers, educators, and industry leaders to work together in realizing the full potential of this integration, ensuring that we equip the next generation with the skills and knowledge necessary for success in an increasingly interconnected world. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for all stakeholders, including policymakers, educators, and industry leaders, as they navigate the complexities of a transforming society. The integration of education, science, and production can significantly influence innovation and economic growth in this new era.

The research between the subjects of the integration of industry and education in higher vocational colleges refers to the process that the interest

subjects contribute to their own behavior according to their own information and ability cognition under certain institutional conditions. The problems in the game of "upgrading", deviation of the government; the problems of dislocation, free riding game and "being idealized"; the lack of function, bad competition and monopoly. Based on this, we should be students-oriented, improve the student interests protection system; pay attention to the actual needs, explore diversified integration of industry and education; optimize the multiple governance path, better play the function of industry organization.

The integration of education and innovation, science and industry is a step-by-step process and its first step is to understand the innovative ecosystem, prepare the legal framework for its creation and its participants on human resources. Another important task is to build educational standards on the basis of integration of knowledge and science, involve young people in the development of science, direct fundamental research to innovative scientific activities, and increase knowledge on the commercialization of new developments. In this regard, the fact that the state has begun to act as a general customer, rather than a general inspector, shows that there is a healthy environment in this process that works on the path of development is carried out on the basis of equality.

REFERENCES:

1. Navruzova Gulrukh Uktamovna, . ANALYSIS OF FACTORS WHICH AFFECTING THE ECONOMIC GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT. Zenodo.<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11223523>.<https://ilmiyxabarlar.uz/index.php/journal/article/view/616/562>
2. Navruzova Gulrukh Uktamovna , STRATEGIES TO IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM <https://webofjournals.com/> Volume 2, issue 5, May,2024
3. Navruzova Gulrukh Uktamovna, . the . assistant . of B. I. E. and M. U. (2024). INNOVATION MANAGEMENT: IMPLEMENTING A SUCCESSFUL STRATEGY.<https://worldejurnal.ru/index.php/ajmws/article/view/94>
4. Vol. 1 No. 2 (2024): American Journal of Modern World Sciences
5. Korajczyk, R. A., & Levy, A. (2003). Capital structure choice: macroeconomic conditions and financial constraints. *Journal of financial economics*, 68(1), 75-109.
6. Kouri, P. J. (1976). The exchange rate and the balance of payments in the short run and in the long run: A monetary approach. *The Scandinavian Journal of Economics*, 280-304.
7. Lefcoe, G. (2011). Competing for the next hundred million Americans: The uses and abuses of tax increment financing. *The Urban Lawyer*, 427-482.
8. Lewis, W. A. (2013). *Theory of economic growth* (Vol. 7). Routledge.
9. Smets, F. (2013). Financial stability and monetary policy: How closely interlinked?. *Sveriges Riksbank Economic Review*, 3, 121-160.
10. Shamsiya, A. (2023). HR MANAGEMENT AND COACHING IN THE INNOVATIVE ECONOMY AS A METHOD OF BUSINESS MANAGEMENT. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 712-717.

11. Abidovna, A. S. (2024). The Importance of Personnel Management in the Operations of an Organization. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 49, 971-975.
12. Alimova, S. O. FEATURES OF THE STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES. Kielce: Laboratorium Wiedzy Artur Borcuch
13. Alimova, S. (2024). NEW APPROACHES TO THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERACTION BETWEEN PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION AND EMPLOYERS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(7), 211-218.
14. Abidovna, A. S. (2024). COMMUNICATION PROCESS MANAGEMENT AS A TOOL TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF MODERN ORGANIZATIONS. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 49, 211-217.
15. Bazarova, M. (2024). MARKETING MANAGEMENT STRATEGY'S IMPORTANCE AND MODERN CONCEPT. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6).
16. Bazarova, M. (2024). FEATURES OF BANKING MANAGEMENT IN THE ACTIVITIES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6)
17. Bazarova, M. S. (2022). FACTORS THAT ENSURE THE SUCCESSFUL IMPLEMENTATION OF A SYSTEM OF KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS IN THE FIELD OF HIGHER EDUCATION. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 582-586.
18. Khudoynazarovich, S. A. (2023). CREATING VALUE IN A TOURIST DESTINATION.
19. Khudoynazarovich, S. A. (2021). An Opportunity of Internet Marketing in Tourism Sphere. *International Journal on Economics, Finance and Sustainable Development*, 3(3), 356-361.
20. Ikromov, E. (2024). SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL BASIS OF INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF SERVICE ENTERPRISES. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 103-109.

21. Ikromov, E. (2024). FEATURES AND ADVANTAGES OF SERVICE ENTERPRISES. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 98-102.
22. Ruzmetov, B., Jumaeva, Z. K., & Xudayarova, M. (2021). International experience in attracting foreign direct investment. *International Journal on Economics, Finance and Sustainable Development*, 3(4), 38-43.
23. Jumayeva, Z. (2024). THE NEED FOR AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH IN MANAGING ORGANIZATIONS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 557-562.
24. Ruzmetov, B., Ruzmetov, S., Bakhtiyarov, S., Dzhumaeva, Z., & Juraev, K. (2023). Formation of supporting points for production growth based on diversification of the regional industry. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 449, p. 01001). EDP Sciences.
25. Jumayeva, Z. Q. (2024). METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF COMPREHENSIVE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMS OF THE REGION BASED ON THE ACTIVATION OF INVESTMENT PROCESSES. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY*, 4(7), 137-140.